

WHEN DO YOU EXERCISE AFTER VEIN TREATMENT?

It is the major question for the person who is a fitness lover but it depends on many factors. The short suggestion to exercising after **veins treatment** is as following:

- Your **vein doctor's** suggestions are very important in the weeks to follow the procedure. Your [vein specialist san jose](#) knows your exact treatment, health, and procedure to bear in mind.
- It is recommended to wear compression stockings for sclerotherapy. You should not do exercise for about 5-7 days.
- For endovenous laser ablation(Laser) or radiofrequency ablation(RFA), it is okay to do exercise, if it feels okay to you. Try to avoid cycling or heavy weight lifting for a couple of days.

Read this full article to understand better the exercising procedure after **vein treatment**.

Exercise after Spider Vein treatment

Spider vein treatment or sclerotherapy does not produce closure of the spider veins as endovenous laser ablation does with the varicose veins. Dependency on compression to seal the smaller veins increases which help in achieving nicer result. The increased blood flow to the legs during exercise may result in veins that are not completely sealed, even with compression stockings.

1.Activities like heavy weight lifting, squatting, and running comes under the high impact exercises which should be avoided for at least 2-3 days or sometimes for a week.

2.1.Low impact activities are encouraged during this time. Low-impact activities like walking, yoga, light weight lifting are most suitable after the sclerotherapy.

Exercises are known to prevent **vein treatment** disease, by improving the blood flow in your legs. So, if you are planning to go for sclerotherapy or laser ablation then you do not have to give up your regular exercise routine.

Exercise after Varicose Vein Surgery

After having **varicose vein treatment** surgery you should do exercising as it helps to regain proper vein function and speed healing. The exercise which receives a green signal from your doctor after having surgery is walking.

During recovery from varicose vein surgery, walking is most critical for some patients. The [varicose vein treatment san jose](#) advised patients to walk for at least 30 minutes after having varicose vein surgery. You are also advised to walk for one hour a day in the following procedure. Because it lowers the chances of the formation of blood clots in the veins.

A patient should not resume high-intensity exercise until they have an ultrasound post-procedure to check that the veins are treated successfully and there is no blood clot

formation. There are no fixed guidelines to start heavy exercise like cycling, weight lifting, or running. Most surgeons recommend avoiding heavy exercises for a minimum of 2 weeks.

For preventing new varicose veins formation the exercise also recommended. Any exercise that works for muscles in the legs is good as it prevents the formation of blood clots in the legs.

If you want to resume exercise, then regarding that you should consult **vein doctor san jose** and your therapist. They will help you out in designing a routine that will prevent the formation of varicose veins in your legs.